

EXPERIMENTAL ASSESSMENT OF STATIC AND FATIGUE DAMAGE OF GRAPHITE/EPOXY LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

This paper is concerned with the damage due to transverse cracking, loss of stiffness, and delamination under static and fatigue loading. Knowledge about this type of damage formation may be useful in providing data for establishing a reliable fatigue life prediction scheme. To accomplish this, the cracks developed in the angle plies during the various stages of loading were observed on the free edge of the specimen using a microscope. Acoustic emission was employed to detect the first ply failure and onset of delamination under static loading. The stiffness change for the $[0/90/\pm 45]_8$ laminate at two fatigue stress levels was measured using strain gages. The observed cracks in each angle ply were presented vs. applied stress and fatigue life. The effect of stacking sequence, ply thickness, and delamination on the transverse crack formation was also considered. An attempt was made to correlate the damage in terms of crack density and stiffness loss to fatigue life.

INTRODUCTION

When a multi-directional composite laminate is subjected to a load history, damage occurs in the weaker plies prior to ultimate failure and this damage multiplies progressively throughout the specimen volume instead of a predominant single crack, which has been observed in most isotropic brittle materials. Fiber break, interface debonding, delamination, and matrix cracking are the common failure mechanisms in composite materials. Any one or combination of these mechanisms is responsible with a different extent of influence in the damage process. This damage results in a reduction of load carrying capability and stiffness of the laminate. The type and degree of damage vary widely depending upon material properties, lamination including stacking sequence and layer thickness, state of stress, etc.

The main objective of this work was to assess the damage related with matrix cracking and delamination under static and fatigue loading in order to improve the knowledge about the damage mechanism in composite materials. An attempt was also made to develop a fatigue life prediction scheme from the observed damage in terms of crack density and stiffness degradation.

To accomplish this objective, the cracks developed in the various stages of loading were observed on the free edges of each specimen under a microscope. The observed crack data in each angle ply was presented with stress level and fatigue life. The effect of stacking sequences and layer thickness on the crack formation was investigated by employing various types of laminates. Acoustic emission technique and radiograph were employed to detect the first ply failure and onset of delamination for some specimens. To study the degradation of stiffness with fatigue life, the axial strain was measured for a number of specimens of $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate at various stages of the fatigue life. The strain measurement was made at two stress levels. In fatigue test, all specimens were tested under tension-tension fatigue with the stress ratio, $R = 0.1$, and a frequency of 10 Hz.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The material system used in this study was T300/5208 graphite/epoxy supplied in prepreg form by Narmco Corporation. Three types of the basic laminates, $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$, $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$ and $[0/90]_S$ were fabricated in an autoclave according to the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle. These specimens were not subjected to post cure. The effect of delamination, ply thickness, and constraint of the adjacent layer on the transverse crack formation of the angle ply were also considered through variation of stacking sequence of the laminates. The laminate with stacking sequence $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ does not show any delamination under static loading, whereas extensive delamination occurs in the laminate $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$ caused by presence of tensile interlaminar normal stress at free edges [1]. The stacking sequences of the other laminates were $[0/90]_{2S}$, $[0_2/90_2]_S$, and $[0/90_3]_S$ which generate data on the effect of layer thickness.

Straight-sided coupon specimens were prepared from the panels using a diamond-impregnated saw. All specimens were 7.6 cm long and 1.9 cm wide in gage section. The side edges of the specimens were ground with sand paper and then polished with 5 and 0.05 micron polishing powder in order to facilitate microscopic examination. All specimens were inspected under a microscope prior to each test to examine any fabrication-induced cracks and then stored in a dry-cabinet to prevent moisture absorption from the laboratory environment.

Microscope was employed to document all the number of cracks of each angle ply developed in 5 cm along the free edge during static and fatigue loading. The specimen was initially loaded to a predetermined level, unloaded, and then removed from the loading frame to examine the cracks. This procedure was repeated with incremental loading until final failure. The stress level at first ply failure which occurred for all the specimens was determined by acoustic emission which was developed in Ref. [2]. The stress level at initiation of delamination for the $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$ laminate was also determined using acoustic emission. It was found that the rate

of acoustic emission signal was rapidly increased with onset of delamination and remained until final failure.

In fatigue test, loss of stiffness in conjunction with cracks was used as a measure for the assessment of fatigue damage. The damage in the form of transverse cracks and loss of stiffness was periodically measured by interrupting fatigue testing. Loss of stiffness was measured with a strain gage mounted on each specimen. Because of the limited fatigue life of a strain gage, a new strain gage mounted in the same position was used for each measurement. The strains in fatigue test were measured only for $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate with the maximum stress levels, 345 and 414 MPa. All specimens were tested using an MTS closed-loop electrohydraulic testing machine with Instron friction type of jaw grips under load control mode.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Damage in the form of transverse crack in each angle ply within the laminate was observed at the free edge of the specimen. Photomicrographs of crack pattern under static loading for $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ and $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$ laminates are presented in Figs 1 and 2, respectively. Each figure shows photomicrographs of four progressively increased loadings. In all the cases, the first crack occurred in the 90° layers and was arrested at the layer interfaces as shown in Figs. 1(a) and 2(a). Examination of the specimen with a radiograph reveals that the cracks had extended through the whole specimen width. The number of cracks increased and were confined for a time in the 90° layers with increasing load. Further increasing load, new cracks occurred in the 45° layers adjacent to the 90° layers. Most of these cracks appeared at the tip of cracks in the 90° layers and extended instantly through the thickness of the layer and were arrested at the layer interface $+45^\circ/-45^\circ$. However, a few cracks extended progressively toward the interface as indicated in Fig. 1(b) through 1(d) and 2(b) and 2(c). Unlike cracks in the 90° layers, most cracks in the 45° layers are angular at the free edge. They appear at angles approximately 50° to 60° from the horizontal. Examination of the specimen sectioned lengthwise through the middle of the width reveals that they are parallel to cracks in the 90° layer.

At about 350 MPa of the applied stress, delamination occurred in the $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$ laminate and extended almost instantly over the entire length of the specimen with irregular paths at the interfaces of the $90^\circ/90^\circ$, $90^\circ/-45^\circ$, and $+45^\circ/-45^\circ$ layers. Scanning of the specimen lengthwise under a microscope reveals that the change of the delamination path usually happened at transverse crack tips. Radiographic examination shows that the delamination was continuously extended toward the middle of the specimen from both free edges as the load increased. No delamination was observed in the $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate under static loading until failure. From the initiation of delamination, the formation of cracks differs for the two stacking sequences. In the $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$ laminate, all the cracks in the 90° layers appear to be extended to the adjacent -45° layers and arrested at the interfaces of the $+45^\circ/-45^\circ$ layers as shown in Figure 2(d). The number of cracks in both the 90° and -45° layers were increased until onset of delamination and thereafter remained in constant until final failure. However, the number of cracks in the 90° and $+45^\circ$ layers in the $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate was continuously increased with increasing load until final failure. It was also observed that some of the cracks in the 90° layers remained without extending to the adjacent layers (the cracks at the upper left corner in Fig. 1(d)). This difference in crack pattern for the two stacking sequences appears to be due to delamination which might release the stress concentration in the surrounding layers or redistribute the stresses in the ply. Most of the specimens of both stacking sequences did not reveal any cracks in the -45° layers ($[0/90/\pm 45]_S$) and the $+45^\circ$ layers ($[0/\pm 45/90]_S$) until final failure as shown in Figs. 1 and 2. In some cases, a few cracks in these layers were observed near the final failure and were not linked to the cracks in the adjacent layers.

In fatigue loading, the crack occurrence in both stacking sequence is similar to the description given previously for static loading. However, fatigue cycling at a given stress level causes additional cracks to form as a function of fatigue cycles endured. Figs. 3 and 4 show the sequence of crack occurrence and axial crack

(a) 345 MPa

(b) 414 MPa

(c) 483 MPa

(d) 552 MPa

Fig. 1. Photomicrographs Showing Crack Patterns Under Static Loading: $[0/90/\pm 45]_s$

or delamination at a variety of cycles for the maximum stress, 345 MPa, for the $[0/90/\pm 45]_s$ and $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$, respectively. In fatigue loading, a number of cracks appeared in the -45° layers for the $[0/90/\pm 45]_s$ and $+45^\circ$ layers for the $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$ as shown in Figs. 3 and 4. Some of these cracks were linked to those in the adjacent layers and the rest were not. In addition to this, axial cracks between layers appeared in the $[0/90/\pm 45]_s$ laminate and grew as the fatigue cycle increased as shown in Fig. 3(b) through 3(d). In order to closely examine the propagation of delamination toward the middle of the specimen width, a few specimens of the $[0/90/\pm 45]_s$ laminate were tested under fatigue at $S_{\max} = 345$ MPa, 414 MPa, and 483 MPa. The progress of delamination was examined using radiographic techniques after interrupting the test. The typical results are shown in Fig. 5. N represents the fatigue life at the respective maximum stress level and the numerals on the left of

(a) 207 MPa

(b) 276 MPa

(c) 345 MPa

(d) 448 MPa

Fig. 2. Photomicrographs Showing Crack Patterns Under Static Loading: $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$

each picture represent the number of cycles endured when the specimen was examined. The growth of delamination is irregular and dependent upon the fatigue cycles endured. The growth rate is largely dependent upon the fatigue stress. The specimen subjected to fatigue loading at $S_{max} = 483$ MPa did not reveal any axial crack until the fatigue failure (Fig. 5(c)). However, some other specimens at the same stress which failed at a higher cycle revealed some delamination on the free edges. It should be noted that the specimen subjected to fatigue at $S_{max} = 414$ MPa (Fig. 5(b)) was broken at the place where the largest delamination occurred.

In the $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$, the delamination at $S_{max} = 345$ MPa occurred in the very early fatigue life, somewhere around 200 cycles, and rapidly propagated toward the middle of the specimen width as cycle increased. Upon the onset of delamination,

(a) 2×10^4 CYCLE

(b) 4×10^4 CYCLE

(c) 20×10^4 CYCLE

(d) 65×10^4 CYCLE

Fig. 3. Photomicrographs Showing Crack Patterns Under Fatigue Loading: $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$, $S_{max} = 345$ MPa; $N = 793,300$ cycle.

the crack formation in the 90° and -45° layers had virtually ceased until final fatigue failure as observed under static loading, whereas the number of cracks in the 45° layers had increased for a time after initiation of delamination. The delaminations occurred in the interfaces of $90^\circ/90^\circ$, $90^\circ/-45^\circ$, and $-45^\circ/+45^\circ$ layers.

The crack data observed in each test was reduced in terms of number of cracks per centimeter in the respective angle ply obtained from the total number of cracks divided by the measured length, five centimeters. Hereafter, this quantity will be referred to as crack density. The inverse of this number will give the average spacing of the crack in a given layer. The crack density will be identical for the middle two layers since cracks in these layers extended across both layers.

(a) 200 CYCLE

(b) 1,000 CYCLE

(c) 2×10^4 CYCLE

(d) 10×10^4 CYCLE

Fig. 4. Photomicrographs Showing Crack Patterns Under Fatigue Loading: $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$, $S_{max} = 345$ MPa

However, the average value of two layers was used for the layers symmetrically positioned about the laminate midplane since the difference between two layers was found to be less than 5% in most cases.

The crack density in each ply for the $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate is plotted as a function of applied stress in Fig. 6. The stress in this figure represents the differential stress obtained by subtracting the stress at the first ply failure from the applied stress. The reason for employing the stress difference was based on the work by Tsai and Hahn [3] which shows that the effective failure region is functionally related with the first ply failure stress. The stress at the first ply failure (σ_{FPF}) detected by acoustic emission is presented with the ultimate strength in

Fig. 5. X-ray Pictures Showing Progress of Delamination Under Fatigue Loading: [0/90/ \pm 45]_s

Fig. 6. The crack densities for both 90° and +45° layers were monotonically increased with stress. Of the seven specimens tested, only one specimen (indicated with a circle) reveals cracks in the middle -45° layers near the failure, and the crack density for the 90° layer approached a limiting state where no further new cracks occurred. The cracks for the other specimens were continuously increased until final failure. Since the general trend of crack behavior obtained for seven specimens is fairly well reproducible, the typical results of each specimen for [0/90/ \pm 45] and [0/ \pm 45/90] are presented in Fig. 7 for comparison. It is worthy to note that there are marked differences between the +45° layer and the -45° layer in the crack density and stress at initiation of the first crack for both laminates as shown in Fig. 7. This difference in onset of the transverse crack between two

Fig. 6. Stress vs. Number of Cracks Under Static Loading for Specimens of [0/90/±45] Laminate. The stress represents a differential stress obtained by subtracting stress at first ply failure from applied stress.

Fig. 7. Applied Stress vs. Number of Cracks Under Static Loading for Comparison of Two Stacking Sequences

layers oriented at opposite angle cannot be adequately explained by a simple laminate analysis. Since the laminate theory will provide identical stress magnitude for each of two layers, a failure theory based on stress or strain magnitude will predict the same stress level for onset of transverse crack. Bader, et al. [4] and Wang [5], et al. applied fracture mechanics concept of the strain energy release rate to describe the crack process dependence on the thickness of 90° layer in cross ply laminates. They reported that the strain level at the onset of transverse crack was increased as decreasing 90° layer thickness. In this study, however, the stress level at onset of transverse crack is considerably smaller in the 45° layers adjacent to 90° layer than in the other 45° layers regardless of the layer thickness as shown in Figs. 6 and 7. Therefore, this difference at the onset of the transverse crack in the 45° layers is believed to be caused by the 90° layer crack which has extended into the adjacent layer with increasing stress.

The difference of crack behavior between two stacking sequences is significant with respect to the crack density and stress level at the crack initiation. Unlike the $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate, in the $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$ laminate the cracks in the -45° layers were immediately followed by the cracks in the 90° layers. Although this discrepancy between different stacking sequences is not understood well at present, strain energy release rate is considered to play a significant role in this case. Since the cracks in the 90° layers in the $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$ laminate extended across both layers whereas in the other laminate there is a single 90° layer, the available energy for crack extension in the double 90° layers will be greater than that in the single 90° layer.

The cracks in both 90° and -45° layers increased monotonically until the onset of delamination and thereafter remained constant until failure as shown in Fig. 7. This observation leads to a conjecture that the delamination causes stress relaxation or reduces stress transfer capability so as to cause crack arrestment. Radiographic examination reveals that the delamination was not confined in the free edge region but propagates rapidly toward the middle of the laminate with increasing load. It is interesting to note that the first ply failure stress for the $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$ agrees fairly well with the theory developed by Hahn and Pagano [6]. However, the ply failure for the other laminate was considerably higher than that of the prediction.

A total of 40 specimens (32 specimens of $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate) were tested under fatigue loading employing several fatigue stress levels. Since all the crack data obtained for all stress levels generally exhibit the similar trends, a typical result for each laminate at maximum fatigue stress of 345 MPa is presented in Fig. 8. In fatigue loading, the number of cracks in each angle ply for the $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ increased compared with those in static loading. But the number of cracks in the 90° and -45° layer for the $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$ is practically identical compared with those in static loading.

As observed in static case, the crack process in the two different stacking sequences is also remarkably different under fatigue loading. It should be noted that the onset of delamination in the $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$ occurred at approximately 200 cycles. The curves for 90° layer (open square) and -45° layer (semi-solid square) in Fig. 8 substantiate the earlier discussion of interference in delamination on transverse cracking. Since the delamination mostly ran along the interfaces of 90°/90° and -45°/90°, the cracking in the +45° layer (solid square) appears to be hardly affected by delamination.

In all cases in Fig. 8, the number of cracks reached to a limiting state where no further new cracks occurred thereafter in spite of increasing fatigue cycle. The recent work by Reifsnider, et al. [7] referred this limiting state to a characteristic damage state and concluded that the characteristic damage state is a well-defined material property independent of load history. However, in this study, most of the specimens of $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate under static loading failed without revealing the limiting state and the number of cracks observed are smaller than those in fatigue loading.

Fig. 8. Fatigue Cycle vs. Number of Cracks for $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ and $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$ Laminate

In order to look at the limiting state for a variety of fatigue stress levels, the total number of cracks are plotted as a function of fatigue stress as shown in Fig. 9. The total number of cracks represents an algebraic sum of the cracks in each angle ply. The circle is the average value of the total number of cracks for specimens tested at each stress level. Eight specimens were tested at stress levels, 345 MPa and 414 MPa, and four specimens each at the other stress. The number of cracks at the limiting state appears to be identical in the lower fatigue stress range and decreased as the stress level increased. Although most of the specimens definitely exhibited the limiting state before fatigue failure, some specimens at 414 MPa and 448 MPa, and all specimens at 483 MPa did not exhibit the limiting state until the last measurement was taken. The last measurement taken for each specimen varies widely dependent upon fatigue life and was in the range of 80% to 99% of total cycle to failure. The measured number of cracks prior to failure may not precisely represent the number that would have presented at final failure. Since most cracks occurred in the early stage of fatigue life (more than 95% of cracks occurred at 70% of life), the effect of measurement time on the total number of cracks appears to be very minimal. Therefore, we can conclude that the specimen above a certain fatigue level will fail before reaching the limiting state due to strength degradation incurred during cyclic loading.

The number of cracks in a layer found to be dependent upon the ply thickness. For the $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate, the total number of cracks in single 45° layer was much greater than those in double 45° layers as shown in Fig. 8. To substantiate the thickness influence, cross ply laminates having various thickness of 90° layer were tested under fatigue loading until reaching the limiting state. The number of cracks observed is plotted as a function of ply thickness in Fig. 10. These data were obtained from three laminates, $[0/90]_S$, $[0_2/90_2]_S$, and $[0/90_3]_S$ that provide one, two, four and six of 90° layer surrounded by 0° layer. Wang, et al. found the similar trend of crack dependence on the ply thickness employing energy release rate [5].

Fig. 9. Number of Cracks at Limiting State as Function of Fatigue Stress Level for $[0/90/\pm 45]_s$ Laminate

Fig. 10. Number of 90° Layer vs. Number of Cracks at Limiting State Obtained from $[0/90]_{2s}$, $[0_2/90_2]_s$ and $[0/90_3]_s$ Laminates

Fig. 11 presented the transverse crack data for all the specimen tested under fatigue loading except for those at fatigue stresses, 310 MPa and 483 MPa. Damage ratio in the ordinate was obtained from number of cracks at a certain fatigue cycle divided by number of cracks at or near fatigue failure. A total of 18 specimens were involved in Fig. 11. As described previously, the most transverse cracking occurred in the earlier fatigue life for all the specimens. Approximately 80% of total crack appeared in the range of 20% to 55% of fatigue life. The transverse cracks appear to be related with the cycle ratio independent of the fatigue stress

Fig. 11. Cycle Ratio vs. Fatigue Damage Ratio for the $[0/90/\pm 45]_s$ Laminate

employed in Fig. 11. However, the use of transverse cracks alone for the fatigue control is questionable at present, mainly due to wide spread of data.

Stiffness reduction incurred during fatigue loading for $[0/90/\pm 45]_s$ laminate was observed at two fatigue stress levels, 345 MPa and 414 MPa. A total of six specimens were tested to obtain three replicas for each stress level. Fig. 12 shows the stiffness reduction as a function of cycle ratio except for the early cycle. Thereafter, the rate of stiffness reduction is apparently identical regardless of the fatigue stress level employed. The degree of stiffness reduction in early fatigue life is more prominent in lower stress level in this laminate. The transverse cracking appears to be solely responsible for the initial reduction in stiffness since delamination occurred much later. And no fiber breaks in the 0° layers are expected to occur at such an early stage of fatigue cycle. However, after sudden reduction of stiffness in the early cycle, some other failure mechanisms such as delamination and fiber breaks may be involved in the stiffness degradation. This can be easily understood in considering the constant rate of stiffness reduction until final fatigue failure while the rate of cracking decreased drastically with fatigue cycle as shown in Fig. 11. Since the fatigue failure normally occurs when the residual strength reaches the maximum fatigue stress [8], the degree of damage at the time of failure will be more extensive in lower stress level than in higher stress level.

The stiffness reduction at the time of fatigue failure can provide information on the loss in load carrying capability of the angle plies due to fatigue damage. Assuming that the angle plies failed with complete loss in load carrying capability while the 0° layers remained intact, the stiffness will reduce to 66% of the original stiffness for this laminate. However, the stiffness at most was reduced to 78% as shown in Fig. 12. Therefore, we can conclude that the angle plies are still able to partially carry the load in spite of such extensive damage.

CONCLUSIONS

An experimental investigation has been conducted on the damages related with transverse crack and delamination which occurred during static loading and fatigue loading. Following are the conclusions based on the experimental observation:

Fig. 12. Change of Stiffness as Function of Cycle Ratio for $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ Laminate

- (1) In static loading the number of cracks increased continuously with stress level until final failure for the $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate which did not reveal delamination. In the $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$ laminate, the crack density increased until onset of delamination, and the crack density in the layers in the vicinity of the delamination path remained constant until final failure. Thus, delamination appears to arrest the multiplication of transverse crack.
- (2) In fatigue testing most of the transverse cracks developed in early fatigue cycle and the crack density at lower stresses reached a limiting state prior to final fatigue failure. However, at higher stress level, specimen failed without revealing the limiting state. The $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate which did not reveal delamination under static loading did show delamination in early fatigue life, which grew toward the middle of specimen width with increasing fatigue cycle.
- (3) The ply thickness seems to play an important role in crack formation and extension of the cracks into the adjacent layers.
- (4) A strong correlation between damage ratio based on transverse crack and cyclic ratio appears to exist for the $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate. Although the crack data provides invaluable information about the damage process, the prospects for establishing a fatigue life prediction scheme based on this information alone is quite questionable at present, mainly due to a large change in slope during the early portion of the curve (Fig. 11) and large scatter of the data.
- (5) Stiffness ratio is linearly related with the cyclic ratio for the $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate. This linear relationship appears to be promising for the prediction of fatigue life.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author wishes to acknowledge R. Esterline and R. Cornwell of the University of Dayton Research Institute for preparation of testing specimens. This work was sponsored by the Nonmetallic Materials Division, Air Force Materials Laboratory, under Contract No. F33615-78-C-5102.